

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

TO DETERMINE THE OCCURRENCE OF DEPRESSION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS C (HCV) DURING ANTIVIRAL THERAPY; A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY

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Article Received: October 2020 Accepted: November 2020 Published: December 2020

Abstract:

Objective: The aim of our study was to find out the occurrence of depression in Patients with chronic Hepatitis C (HCV) during antiviral therapy.

Study Design: A Cross sectional study

Place and Duration: This study was conducted at medicine department of District Headquarter Hospital, Bahawalnagar for the duration of five months starting from March 2020 to August 2020.

Methodology: In the study we included young Hepatitis C patients of both genders. Those patients were not included who were having human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and hepatocellular carcinoma. We used sampling technique of Nonprobability consecutive. We took an informed consent after enrollment of patients according to pre-decided criteria. Data was collected according to pre-designed questionnaire. SPSS v.20 was used for analysis of data.

Results: In the present study we selected a total number of 50 patients of HCV. Their age was 18-60 years with Mean±SD age as 40.50±15.2. In selected patients 36% patients were below 30 years of age, 64% patients were above 30 years of age and 48% were having depression. The patients having age above 30 years were 17 patients with depression and their percentage was 34% and the patients having age below 30 years were 7 patients with depression and their percentage were 14%. 24 patients (48%) having depression, 7 patients (14%) were having normal depression, 9 patients (18%) were having intance depression and 8 patients (16%) with mild depression. 3 (6%) patients were seen for depression during treatment in 2nd month and 11 (22%) patients were seen for depression during treatment in 3rd month and 20% (10) patients were seen for depression during treatment from 4th to 6th month with the P-value of 0.306. Maximum number of patients with depression were calculated in the 3rd month of treatment.

Conclusion: At the end of our study, we concluded that depression is very often in the people of Pakistan during antiviral therapy of hepatitis C patients. Depression is most common in patients over the age of 30.

Key words: Antiviral Therapy, Depression And HCV.

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Please cite this article in press Momal Zahra et al., *To Determine The Occurrence Of Depression In Patients With Chronic Hepatitis C (HCV) During Antiviral Therapy; A Cross Sectional Study*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection is a global health problem that affects about 185 million people with an estimated prevalence of 2.8% [1]. Not only increasing mortality and morbidity of HCV related advanced liver diseases, but also patient-reported outcomes, including quality of life or mental health status led to a significant global disease. Chronic hepatitis C is an infection caused by hepatotropic virus called HCV that infects the liver and may lead to cirrhosis of liver complicated by HCC and decompensation of liver. Usually, acute hepatitis C causes extrahepatic manifestations most commonly involving joints, muscles and skin. Acute HCV has good response to treatment and a chance to clear the virus after interferon treatment. Patients in need of treatment are those having advanced fibrosis, compensated cirrhosis, liver transplant recipients and those with extra hepatic manifestations. Primary goal of treatment is to achieve the sustained eradication of HCV. The second goal is to prevent progression to cirrhosis, HCC and decompensated liver disease requiring liver transplant. Treatment is recommended for patients with high ALT, Age greater than 18 years. Positive PCR for HCV RNA, compensated liver disease (No history of Ascites), Hb>13-12 g/dl, WBC>1500 and Creatinine<1.5. The treatment of HCV advanced over many years. Initially IFN monotherapy was used and then addition of Ribavirin was done. IFN alpha has been used in chronic HCV patients in a dose of 3 Million IU Subcutaneous injections 3 times per week for 24 weeks. Side effects of IFN therapy include fatigue (8-90%). Fever (34-94%), Neutropenia (92%). Flu like syndrome (29%), Myalgia (28-75%), Anorexia (1-69%), Leukopenia (68%), Nausea (17-66%), Elevation of transaminase (13-63%), Weakness (63%), Headache 21-62%, Chills 54% and Diarrhea is reported in 2-45%, Rigors 42%. Many chronic diseases cause depression in majority of patients [2,3]. Previous studies in Western countries showed that patients with chronic HCV infection were associated with high prevalence of psychiatric and neurologic abnormalities and reported in up to 40% of patients on IFN therapy for Chronic HCV leading to suicidal ideation/attempts and actual suicide. Pegylated interferon α and ribavirin therapy (PR therapy) can induce depression so that uncontrolled pretreatment depression is a major contraindication of PR therapy in chronic hepatitis C (CHC) patients.

Although direct acting antivirals are applied to CHC patients, PR therapy is still widely used in many Asian countries and resource-limited regions [4,5]. Alopecia, dyspnea, somnolence, vomiting and Anorexia are other adverse effects.

Contraindications of IFN therapy include hypersensitivity to human IFN, Alpha Protein, Mouse, egg protein and Neomycin. The above-mentioned depression frequency during interferon therapy in Chronic HCV patients is from Western studies and there are no local large studies available. Therefore, we conducted a study to look for frequency of depression during interferon therapy in our patients.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at of District Headquarter Hospital, Bahawalnagar for the duration of five months starting from March 2020 to August 2020. In the study we included 50 young Hepatitis C patients of both genders. Those patients were not included who were having human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and hepatocellular carcinoma. We used sampling technique of Nonprobability consecutive. We took an informed consent after enrollment of patients according to pre-decided criteria. For screening of depression, ICD 10 criteria for the diagnosis of depression were used for each patient [6,7]. The standardized range of ICD 10 for depression patients were categorized as mild depression, moderate and severe depression. A chi square test was applied regarding frequency of depression. A p-value of <0.05 was considered to indicate a statistically significant difference. Data was collected according to pre-designed questionnaire. SPSS v.20 was used for analysis of data.

RESULTS:

In the present study we selected a total number of 50 patients of HCV. Their age was 18-60 years with Mean \pm SD age as 40.50 \pm 15.2. 3 (6%) patients were seen for depression during treatment in 2nd month and 11 (22%) patients were seen for depression during treatment in 3rd month and 20% (10) patients were seen for depression during treatment from 4th to 6th month with the P-value of 0.306. Maximum number of patients with depression were calculated in the 3rd month of treatment.

Table No 01: Patients Seen in Different Months of Treatment

Months	Patients	Percentage
2 nd	03	06%
3 rd	11	22%
4 th – 6 th	10	20%

Out of these 50 patients (48%) had depression. Regarding age distribution, 36% were below 30 years of age and 64% were above 30. Patients below 30 years with depression were 14% (7) and patients above 30 years having depression were 34% (17 patients)

Table No 02: Showing Different Age Groups

Age	Patient	Percentage
<=30 years	18	36%
31-40 years	25	50%
40 years	7	64%

Out of 48% (24 patients) having depression, 16% (8) had mild depression and 14% (7) had moderate depression and 18% (9) had severe depression.

Table No 03: Percentage of Patients in Different Grades of Depression

Depression Type	Patients	Percentage
Mild	08	16%
Moderate	07	14%
Severe	09	18%
Total	24	48%

DISCUSSION:

patients with HCV are increasing worldwide day by day and there are more and more concerns about complications of hepatitis C virus. Depression is associated with HCV patient and it is more common in patients of HCV with antiviral therapy ranging from 2% to 82% in different studies [8,9,10,11]. In a study conducted by Lucas Pereira Jorge de Modeiros et al published in Feb 2014 on fifty HCV patients, 46 % patients were found to have depression which is almost comparable to our finding of 48% patients with depression [12]. In another study by Izabel Lligouri et al was published in Jan/Mar. 2016 on HCV patients on interferon therapy patients were followed for evaluation regarding depression. 32 patients were included in this study with mean age 54 ± 11 [13] years. Depression was found in 25 % of patients and there was more trend of females with depression, although 25 % is lower percentage than our study. There may be geographical difference and secondly the population under study was small (32 patients

only) [14]. In study published in Egyptian journal by Eman R, Elsafy et al, [15]. 100 patients with HCV were enrolled. Prevalence of depression in treated cases was 40%, which is comparable to our finding of 48%. This slight difference may be due to geographical population under study [15]. In a study of by Joo Yeong Baeg et al was done in Korean republic 2017. There were 114 patients of HCV and depression symptom were developed in 34.6% of patients receiving antiviral therapy which is also favoring our results although slightly less than our study but still showing higher percentage of patients developing depression during antiviral therapy [16].

In a study conducted by Vitale G et al in advances in pharmacoepidemiology and drug safety 2015 in Italy. In this study 590 patients were included. Mean age was 54 ± 13 years. In this study new onset of depression and psychiatric symptoms on interferon therapy was found to be 49.2% of patients. That is

almost comparable to our finding of 48% favoring our study [17,18].

CONCLUSION:

At the end of our study, we concluded that depression is very often in the people of Pakistan during antiviral therapy of hepatitis C patients. Depression is most common in patients over the age of 30.

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